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The Percentage of Agricultural Land at World Level

It decreased by an average of 0.5% between 2010 and 2021

The World Bank calculates the percentage of land devoted to agricultural cultivation as a percentage of total land at the country level. Agricultural land refers to the share of arable land, with permanent crops and permanent pastures. Arable land includes land defined by FAO as land under temporary crops, temporary grassland for mowing or grazing, land under market or vegetable gardening and land temporarily fallow. Land abandoned due to cultivation shifts is excluded. Land under permanent crops is land planted with crops that occupy the land for long periods and do not need to be replanted after each harvest, such as cocoa, coffee, and rubber. This category includes land under flowering shrubs, fruit trees, nut trees and vines, but excludes land under trees grown for lumber or lumber. Permanent pasture is land used for five or more years for forage, including natural and cultivated crops.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage of land used for agriculture in 2020. Lesotho ranks first for the percentage of land used for agriculture in 2020 with a value of 85.64%, followed by Saudi Arabia with an amount of 80.75%, from Uruguay with 80.35%, from South Africa with 79.42%, and from Kazakhstan with 79.27%. In the middle of the table are Senegal with 46.11%, Sao Tome and Principe with 45.83%, Angola with 45.68%, the Czech Republic with 45.65%, Botswana with 45.63%, and Greece with 45.52%. The Bahamas closes the ranking with a value of 1.40%, followed by the Northern Mariana Islands with 1.17%, Turks and Caicos Islands with 1.05%, Singapore with 0.92%, and Greenland with 0.59%. Suriname with 0.54%.

Ranking of countries by value of the percentage change of land destined for agriculture between 2010 and 2020. San Marino is in first place for value of the percentage change of land destined for agriculture with a value equal to 130%, followed by Israel with a value of 28.13%, from Samoa with a value of 21.2%, from the West Bank and Gaza with an amount of 18.67%, and Republic of the Congo with an amount of 18.09%. In the middle of the ranking with a value of zero are a group of countries, including Papua New Guinea, Russian Federation, Eswatini, Turks and Caicos Islands, Trinidad and Tobago, Tuvalu. The Marshall Islands close the ranking with a value of -33.85%, followed by the Seychelles with a value of -35.42%, Sudan with -35.68%, Montenegro with a value of -49.62%, and from Northern Mariana Islands with a value of -68.24%.

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Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. A clustering carried out with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method is presented below.

- *Cluster 1:* Uzbekistan, Afghanistan, Hungary, Guinea, Armenia, El Salvador, China, Malawi, Ghana, Romania, The Gambia, Tuvalu, India, Kyrgyz Republic, Cuba, Netherlands, Sierra Leone, Spain, France, Eritrea, Marshall Islands, Tunisia, Mozambique, Greece, Luxembourg, Mexico.
- *Cluster 2:* Nauru, Antigua and Barbuda, Cameroon, Cabo Verde, Myanmar, Chile, Iraq, Peru, Puerto Rico, North Korea, Maldives, Liberia, Iceland, Estonia, Timor-Leste, American Samoa, St. Vincent And the Grenadines, St. Kittis and Nevis, Samoa, South Korea, Grenada, Algeria, Fiji, Venezuela, St Lucia, Malaysia, Vanuatu, Ecuador, Montenegro, Israel, Croatia;
- *Cluster 3:* Malta, Zambia, Ethiopia, Austria, Dominica, Micronesia, Cambodia, Congo, Guam, Mali, Liechtenstein, Indonesia, Slovenia, Honduras, Benin, Latvia, Tajikistan, Bolivia, Georgia, Panama, Costa Rica, Guatemala, Nepal, Nigeria, Iran, Brazil, Guinea Bissau, Vietnam, Barbados, San Marino;
- *Cluster 4:* Bermuda, Guyana, Qatar, United Arab Emirates, Canada, Hong Kong, Equatorial Guinea, Oman, Belize, Solomon Islands, Sweden, Finland, Egypt, Seychelles, Central African Republic, Norway, Northern Mariana Islands, Papua New Guinea , Brunei Darussalam, Gabon, Kuwait, Libya, The Bahamas, Turks and Caicos Islands, Singapore, Palau, Greenland, Suriname, Lao PDR, New Caledonia, Trinidad and Tobago, Aruba, Bahrain, Virgin Islands, Cayman Islands, Jordan, Japan, Cyprus, Russian Federation, French Polynesia, Bhutan, Congo;
- *Cluster 5:* Mongolia, Djibouti, Turkmenistan, Rwanda, Uganda, Ukraine, United Kingdom, Eswatini, Nigeria, Comoros, Bangladesh, Syrian Arab Republic, Somalia, Madagascar, Lesotho, Moldova, Burundi, Togo, Isle of Man, South Africa, Kazakhstan, Saudi Arabia, Faroe Islands, Uruguay, West Bank and Gaza, Morocco, Haiti, Cote d'Ivoire, Denmark, Ireland, Lebanon.
- *Cluster 6:* Yemen, United States, Belgium, Burkina Faso, Sri Lanka, Angola, Albania, Czechia, Tanzania, Botswana, Thailand, Mauritius, Italy, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Belarus, Sao Tome and Principe, Nicaragua, Bulgaria, Kiribati, Zimbabwe, British Virgin Islands, Lithuania, Senegal, Argentina, Philippines, Paraguay, Namibia, Pakistan, Poland, New Zealand, Tonga, Jamaica, Germany, Andorra, Colombia, Portugal, Australia, Kenya, Serbia, Chad, Slovak Republic, North Macedonia , Sudan, Dominican Republic, Turkey, Switzerland, Mauritania.

From the point of view of the median, it is possible to identify the following ordering of the clusters, namely: $C5=71.32 > C1=57.71 > C6=44.38 > C3=32.99 > C2=20.29 > C4=7, 42$.

Conclusions. The data analyzed show that on average the percentage of agricultural land decreased by 0.5 between 2010 and 2021. There are some countries that still have a high percentage of agricultural land such as, for example, the countries of Cluster 5. In average the percentage of agricultural land at the level in 2021 amounted to an amount of 37.25%. Cluster 5 countries have a median percentage of agricultural land amounting to 71.32%. The reasons that drive countries to increase the percentage of agricultural land can be both geographical and economic. From a geographical point of view, it is probable that there are countries that have a particular condition that allows the efficient development of the agricultural sector. However, there may also be economic reasons that can lead a country to increase the percentage of agricultural land. These are countries that have a low per capita income and that have difficulties in implementing industrial systems and

the service sector. Indeed, countries that have a high share of the service sector in terms of GDP also tend to have a small share of land devoted to agriculture.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Plot of total within cluster squared distances (toy data)

